

Physical Barriers

**Difficulty in
movement and
motion for
example due to
a tremor**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Bigger or easier
to use buttons?

Help?

Physical Barriers

Difficulty using a touchscreen

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Bigger or easier
to use buttons?

Customisation?

Help?

Physical Barriers

Difficulty using
external
hardware/devices

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Physical Barriers

Visual impairment

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Bigger or easier
to use buttons?

Help?

Physical Barriers

**Difficulty
reading
when font
is too small**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Customisation?

Help?

Physical Barriers

Difficulty with speech and language

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Physical Barriers

**Difficulty
with spatial
navigation
and getting
lost**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

